

THE NEW CONSTITUTION OF UZBEKISTAN GUARANTEES HUMAN RIGHTS

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Abstract: This article is about how much importance is given to ensuring human rights in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023 in the changes made to the Constitution.

Key words: Constitution, human rights, social state, democracy, article, preamble, chapter, section.

As the society is boldly moving towards rapid development, it is natural that new laws and decisions are needed on this road, based on this, it can be said that the Constitution, which is the main support of the state, is amended from time to time is an extremely positive situation. is considered because the Constitution defines the state structure, the system of power and management bodies, their authority and formation procedure, the electoral system, the rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as the judicial system. The Constitution is the basis of all other laws.

The Republic of Uzbekistan also chose a good way to establish a strong civil society and, as a social state, to further improve the Constitution, to support our people. Accordingly, on May 2022, the Oliy Majlis of Uzbekistan will deal with the implementation of proposals and organizational measures on the Legislation and amendments to the Constitution at a joint meeting of the Councils of the Senate and the Legislative Chamber. A commission was established and this commission was tasked with thoroughly studying each proposal.

All opportunities were created for citizens to express their suggestions in the improvement of the constitution. We can mention that the freedom to apply through the Menin konstitutsiyam.uz portal, a special Telegram-bot and Call-centers has been created. Our Constitution could be amended at the meeting of the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis, but amendments and additions were developed taking into account the opinions and suggestions of every citizen, every person in our country. The Constitution of New Uzbekistan, with amendments and additions, was determined to consist of a preamble, 6 sections, 27 chapters and 155 articles, and was submitted for public discussion on April 30, 2023 a referendum was held throughout Uzbekistan, in which every citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan voted by secret ballot on the basis of general, equal and direct suffrage. According to the results, almost 90% of the people who participated in the referendum voted in favor, which means that our nation is determined to follow the path of rapid development.

The Constitution of the new Uzbekistan deserves to be called a truly populist Constitution, because the fact that the Republic of Uzbekistan is a democratic, legal, social and secular state in Article 1 of our Constitution [1] shows that this Constitution is a guarantee of human rights. means The proposal to include the phrase "social state" in this article in the Constitution was introduced by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "In a word, the state is a place where men and women, families and children, young people and intellectuals, persons with

disabilities, regardless of whether they are in the country or outside it. care for all people should be strengthened in the Constitution," says Shavkat Mirziyoyev.[2] In his speech, the President proposed to include in the Constitution norms that are important in ensuring human rights, such as the "Miranda Rule" and "Habeas Corpus", and one of the most important proposals made by the President is the complete prohibition of the death penalty. is the norm about The main part of the amendments and additions to our constitution is aimed at increasing the level of human rights protection in Uzbekistan, for example: "Human rights and freedoms are directly applicable. Human rights and freedoms determine the nature and content of the activities of laws, state bodies, citizens' self-governance bodies, and their officials" [3] in the Constitution now means that every state body and officials work only for the benefit of citizens.

The norms included in the Constitution mean that the privacy of a person is further strengthened. Also, a person should not be detained for more than 48 hours without a court decision, during the detention of a person, his rights and the grounds for detention must be explained to him in an understandable language, all doubts about guilt, if the possibilities of eliminating them have been exhausted, the suspect, the accused, the defendant or to be decided in favor of the prisoner, if the person's confession is the only evidence against him, he cannot be found guilty or punished, the persons deprived of their freedom should be treated humanely and be humane. have the right to have their honor and dignity respected, that a person's conviction and the resulting legal consequences cannot be a basis for restricting the rights of his relatives, that anyone convicted of a crime may have his sentence reviewed by a higher court in accordance with the procedure established by law right of withdrawal, as well as the right to petition for pardon or mitigation of punishment, the rights of victims of crimes should be protected by law, the state should provide victims with protection and access to justice, and create conditions for compensation for the damage caused to them. and in the social sphere, the development of the state healthcare system, its state and non-state forms, various types of medical insurance, taking measures to ensure sanitary and epidemiological peace of the population, development of physical education and sports, population education to create conditions for the formation of a healthy lifestyle among children, to prohibit any forms of child labor that endanger the child's health, safety, morals, mental and physical development, including the child's education, to work the minimum amount of payment is determined taking into account the need to ensure a decent standard of living of a person, at the level of the Constitution of the norms on the prohibition of refusing to hire women, dismissing them and reducing their wages due to pregnancy or having a child strengthening means that the level of strengthening of the rights of citizens in personal, social and other spheres has increased several times in our republic.

In short, the Updates are aimed not only at personal rights, but also at creating conditions for citizens to fully exercise their rights and turning our country into a social state with a strong civil society. One of the main goals should be to achieve the implementation of these norms, because the society can officially develop only when the laws in the state work not only on paper, but in real life.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 30.04.2023 - 4 p. Article 1

2. Report of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the meeting with the members of the Constitutional Commission on June 20, 2022
3. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 30.04.2023 - 9 p.m. Article 20

